

Social media and Public Service Interpreting and Translation: the *Global E-Party en TISP*

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ABSTRACT: *Social media platforms are rooted in society and have become powerful communication tools. Conversely, Public Service Interpreting and Translation (PSIT) services have not yet been professionalized in some countries such as Spain. Even after having gained prominence in academic/scientific settings, the media presence of PSIT is still underrepresented—mainly on social media—. By using Google search engines, some media gaps needing to be filled were detected. This, in turn, led to the idea of studying whether or not there could be a relationship between the current situation of the non-professionalization of PSIT and the scarcity of its presence on social media. With this in mind, the first Global E-Party en TISP was launched, which is an innovative conference that has been organized every year since 2012 through different social media. Its main objective is to help PSIT attain greater recognition by applying the power of the media to improve its status. The purpose of this paper is to elaborate on the main conclusions that were drawn from the first four times this Global E-Party en TISP has been held.*

KEYWORDS: *PSIT, social media, media visibility, media presence, professionalization.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media is a very common term which refers to the “wide range of Internet-based and mobile services that allow users to participate in online exchanges, contribute to user-created content, or join online communities [1].” These 2.0 websites, therefore, facilitate the potential for social action, interaction, communication, and identity formation in cyberspace, in addition to supplementing and influencing offline social and cultural processes [2].

As is widely known, social media platforms have become rooted in society and act as powerful communication tools that enable people to be in contact with others from all around the world. In addition, these sites are generally communities created to support a common theme or motive, giving individuals the opportunity to not only meet others, but also discuss something that “connects” them on personal and professional levels. These platforms allow peoples’ creations and thoughts to be presented to the masses, potentially providing enriching knowledge on a specific subject. If used correctly, social media can be a means to inform, educate, and raise awareness on a particular topic and/or fight for a common goal. These platforms play critical roles in contemporary societies [3] and can play even more important roles in professional societies, if used in a beneficial manner.

Collectively, Public Service Interpreting and Translation (PSIT) is a field that “makes it possible for individuals and communities to access public services who do not speak the language that the service is provided in [4].” It has not yet been professionalized in Spain or in other countries such as France, Italy, and Greece. As a result, the current status of many PSIT practitioners has led to ridiculous salaries, poor working conditions, professional intrusion, and low prestige of the job and of the people qualified to practice it [5]. This causes training and working as a professional public service translator or interpreter to be somewhat unpleasant. For this reason, various studies have been conducted to uncover the motives behind this current situation and identify any possible solutions to change it. The publications derived from the International Conference on PSIT held at the University of Alcalá since 2002 provide enough evidence [6-10].

However, a review of these publications revealed little or no interest in the presence of PSIT in social media. This lack of research indicated a lack of data. This situation was surprising considering the influence of social media in today’s society. In order to contribute to make PSIT more visible, in 2012 the first edition of the *Global E-Party en TISP* (its Spanish name) was organized. Since then, different editions have been held annually. The methodology and the results obtained will be presented below.

Therefore, this will allow to test whether or not there was a relationship between the current situation of the non-professionalization of PSIT and the scarcity of its social media presence/visibility.

Some results derived from this conclusive study revealed that the prominence of PSIT has increased due to international conferences, publications, and training opportunities. Nonetheless, in some countries such as Spain, the access to this information is limited not only because of the low number of online publications

addressing this area of Translation and Interpreting Studies, but also because of its limited prevalence on social media.

II. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS: THE *GLOBAL E-PARTY EN TISP* PROJECT

By using the Google search engine to look up some key words and expressions, such as “Public Service Interpreting and Translation,” “Community Interpreting and Translation,” and “PSIT,” minor media visibility of this area of Translation and Interpreting Studies was detected. This visibility was more limited or even nonexistent on social media, including various types of platforms such as blogs, wikis, social bookmarking sites, social networking sites, status-update services, virtual world content, and media-sharing sites [1]. This led to the idea in 2012 of studying whether or not there could be a relationship between the current situation of the non-professionalization of PSIT and the scarcity of its presence/visibility on social media. As a result, an innovative conference called the *Global E-Party en TISP* was launched in an attempt to help bridge the relevant gaps, as evidenced in the low number of results obtained from the Google search engine. The three main objectives included: (1) sharing ideas, opinions, projects, materials, experiences, etc. about PSIT; (2) giving PSIT increased media prominence and visibility; and (3) creating, in short, a common system able to inform of/and fight for the need and importance of PSIT and its professionalization in modern societies.

2.1. *Global E-Party en TISP, 1st Edition*

In 2012, the first edition of the *Global E-Party en TISP* was organized within the framework of “Science Week” in Madrid via Blogger, YouTube, Twitter, Foroactivo, and face-to-face workshops. Its motto was “PSIT, reality or fiction?” (“TISP, ¿realidad o ficción?” in Spanish) because the main objective was to help PSIT gain wider media visibility and raise awareness on its relevance and the importance of professionalizing PSIT in modern societies. This event mainly addressed translators and interpreters collectively. Nonetheless, anyone who was interested in this field was able to participate, regardless of their country of origin or language of use.

Figure 1. *Global E-Party en TISP* flyer 1st edition. Issued in the University of Alcalá and through social media and by e-mail.

For three consecutive days, social media users were presented with questions pertaining to the concept of PSIT and its current status in Spain and some other countries. Each social media platform/service had its own role:

- Blogger (<http://globaleparty.blogspot.com.es/>) had an informative and promotional role;
- YouTube (<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M2xUDzjqZYA>) had an advertising role;
- Twitter (@GlobalPartyTISP) had the role of promoting short and fast discussions by using specific hashtags such as #TISPconcepto or #TISPpanorama;
- Foroactivo (<http://globaleparty.foroactivo.com/>) had the role of dealing with the questions that were asked in an elaborative manner, due to the fact that there is no character limit, as is the case with some other websites.
- Face-to-face workshops were also held to discuss these same topics.

Two general and open questions were asked during the first session of this activity in Foroactivo: 1) “What specific skills do you think public service translators/interpreters need?” 2) “Do you think just knowing two languages is enough to work as a translator/interpreter (mainly in the context of public services)?”

A very interesting discussion also began on Twitter about the fact that the roles of interpreters and cultural mediators are still somewhat undefined. This brought codes of ethics and the basic principles regarding the correct practice of professional public service interpreters into question. In this manner, participants could agree or disagree about whether or not an interpreter should mediate/intervene in certain situations. Those who disagreed felt that mediation would mean a loss of impartiality/neutrality as it pertains to the role of an interpreter. Those who defended mediation claimed that facilitating communication between participants was simply another part of the job which, at the end of the day, is an interpreter’s goal.

The results of this first edition were very promising. To demonstrate this, each of the social media platforms used will be mentioned one by one, given that they all contributed in their own ways:

- Blogger: The *Global E-Party en TISP* blog managed to get 2,000 views between the 12th–14th of November of 2012. By April 20th, 2013, 2,481 views had been reached due to the fact that the blog was kept active and updated. For this reason, entry numbers also rose to 18. The blog received a total of three comments during this event. A total of seven languages were used to share information through various publications thanks to the collaboration of the Master's Degree in Intercultural Communication, Public Service Interpreting and Translation offered at the University of Alcalá. In descending order, the countries that had the highest number of views were Spain, the United States, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Germany, Russia, France, Latvia, China, and Israel. The browsers that were most frequently used to gain these views were Firefox, Chrome, Internet Explorer, and Safari, whereas the most commonly used operating systems were Windows, Macintosh, Other Unix, Android, and iPhone.

- Twitter: The @GlobalPartyTISP profile obtained 125 followers over the course of the three sessions. From there, a total of 442 tweets were posted using nine different hashtags. By April 20th, 2013, the number of tweets was slightly higher, at 462. Some of these tweets were written in languages other than Spanish, mainly Mandarin and English.

- Foroactivo: A total of 37 people registered as members on Foroactivo, despite the fact that not all of them participated by leaving comments. By November 14th, 2012, the total number of published messages had risen to 151. The open question was, “What abilities should a public service translator/interpreter specifically have?” Four responses were received, but none of these mentioned the importance of a code of ethics, instead focusing on pragmatic knowledge and cultural differences. The second question was, “Do you think knowing just two languages is enough to work as a translator/interpreter (mainly in the context of public services)?” Again, four users answered, but this time they alluded to a code of ethics and mentioned the importance of knowing and having specific training abiding by a code of ethics. The majority of forum users wrote every day during the *Global E-Party en TISP* and gave different opinions on the discussion threads that were suggested for each session, due in part to the varying profiles of the participants.

It is worth noting that the aforementioned YouTube video had 197 views by April 20th, 2013. The following conclusions have been drawn based on these results:

1. The first *Global E-Party en TISP* was a successful event. There were a lot of participants from various countries who interacted in different languages, leading to a large surge of information on social media regarding PSIT.
2. Due to the positive critical reception of this event, the profiles and accounts created for it remain active.
3. The media presence of PSIT increased, as did its visibility on social media.
4. An array of materials, opinions, and experiences were shared, and a common system was created that was able to provide information on—and fight for—the necessity and importance of PSIT and its professionalization in modern societies.
5. People started to gain clearer understandings regarding PSIT and acquired some basic notions about this field. A huge lack of information and knowledge regarding this specialty of Translation and Interpreting Studies was observed.
6. Overall, this event was repeated the following year, respecting its innovative and dynamic spirit.

2.2. *Global E-Party en TISP, 2nd Edition*

In November 2013, a new *Global E-Party en TISP* was launched, the motto being “Know to Appreciate!” (in Spanish, “¡(Re)conoce!”).

Figure 2. *Global E-Party en TISP* flyer 2nd edition. Issued in the University of Alcalá and through social media and by e-mail.

This second edition focused on issues related to the practice and ethics surrounding PSIT professionals, taking into account the fact that one of the most important elements clearly characterizing a profession is an adherence to a code of ethics. There is still no sole PSIT code of ethics recognized by professionals in different sectors. Nevertheless, there is a general agreement on the basic principles that should be observed, which include accuracy, impartiality, confidentiality, and professionalism. Translators and interpreters often face situations plagued by ethical dilemmas which can compromise their ability to correctly carry out their work. Bearing in mind the importance of a code of ethics for PSIT professionals, it was decided that, through the *Global E-Party en TISP 2*, focus would be maintained on certain aspects of ethics in PSIT, thereby continuing the initiative started by the *Global E-Party en TISP 1*.

Some adjustments were made in order to hold this new edition, taking into account the results and conclusions drawn from the previous year. In this manner, the conference's blog and Twitter profile were actively maintained, and a Facebook account was also created as a means to hold extensive discussions, thereby eliminating the need for face-to-face workshops. Once again, Blogger played an informative/publicity-based role in this event as it had the previous year, but with the addition of brief daily assessments of the development of entry activity. Twitter discussions focused on certain subjects already covered in the previous edition. Nonetheless, some new subjects were added, and the following representative hashtags were created as a result: #TISP, #TISPámbitos, #TISPreconocimiento, #TISPrealidad, #TISPconectados, #TISPanécdotas, #TISPidomas, #TISPredes, #TISPética, #TISPPaíses, #ISP, #TISPvalor, #TISPconclusiones, and #TISPGénero. Meanwhile on Facebook, publications on different topics (which allowed for more extensive responses) were posted under the following headings: "What do We Mean When We Talk about PSIT?," "The Public Service Interpreter," "Information about PSIT on Social Media," "Correct and Incorrect Behavior by Public Service Interpreters and Translators," "The Main Difficulties Faced by Public Service Interpreters and Translators and Possible Strategies for Solving Them," "Resources for Public Service Interpreters and Translators," "Good Practices for Public Service Interpreters," "What's so Special about PSIT?," and "Conclusions Regarding this Initiative."

Figure 3. Sample discussion opened in the Facebook homepage of the *Global E-Party en TISP 2*.

Various short discussions were created on Twitter containing direct questions and interactions about PSIT ethics. The following questions that arose from some of these discussions are worth mentioning: "What abilities should a public service interpreter/translator have?," "Have you ever been faced with a moral dilemma caused by a difficult situation?," "Which principle of the code of ethics is the most difficult to follow?," "What principles should be included in a public service translator's/interpreter's code of ethics?," and "Do you mention a code of ethics in your introduction protocol?" All of these questions led to the direct and indirect participation of various Twitter members by their clicking on the "Favorite," "Retweet," and "Respond" buttons. The results indicated the following:

- Blogger: During the first edition that was held, Blogger had eighteen posts and reached 2,481 views by April 20th, 2013. By the second edition, 25 posts and 3,684 views were tallied. As previously mentioned, Blogger was used merely as an informative/publicity-based platform, which is why it focused on the scope of the event and not on participants' responses to the specific questions that were asked regarding the ethics surrounding PSIT. Participants from the following countries accessed Blogger: Spain (2,042), the United States (620), the United

Kingdom (142), Russia (110), Germany (103), the Netherlands (95), France (53), Ukraine (47), China (34), and Latvia (21).

- Twitter: During the first edition of this event, the Twitter profile page @GlobalPartyTISP gained a total of 125 followers, and 472 tweets were posted on this account. By January 13th, 2014, after the second edition was held, the account had 185 followers and 759 tweets. With a specific focus on analyzing the responses received regarding PSIT ethics, it is worth mentioning that, in response to the question about the abilities required of a public service translator/interpreter, one user outlined the importance of a code of ethics. Regarding the question on the main principles of a code of ethics, only one user mentioned confidentiality, impartiality, accuracy, and integrity, and another user mentioned that one must “stick to what is strictly necessary; objectivity, accuracy and communicative ability.” Another participant used the thread to reveal that compromising situations arise when victims of abuse reveal the abuse they are experiencing to the interpreter but ask the interpreter not to say anything to the social workers or any other professional. Another three users mentioned that the most difficult principle to abide by was impartiality because “we are people and our desire to help causes us, unwittingly, to take sides.” This exchange of opinions is in line with the same debate reflected in studies that were previously published [11-12, 13, 7]. When questioned about whether or not they made some mention of a code of ethics in their introduction protocol, some professional public service translators/interpreters admitted to not talking about a code or mentioning its fundamental principles to the people for whom they were translating or interpreting. In response to specific questions about violence against women, one participant said that one must always be impartial “because this guarantees the correct provision of the service to the victim,” and added that these victims are usually very worried about confidentiality. Lastly, one participant pointed out that telephone interpreting had created its own code of ethics because current codes cannot be applied to this mode of interpreting.

- Facebook: By January 17th, 2014, the Facebook page of the *Global E-Party en TISP* had 120 likes, and 86 posts were made. Users actively participated not only during the three-day session, but also after it had concluded. This session, which was dedicated to ethics surrounding PSIT, was followed on Facebook by an average of 86 people. Nonetheless, there was little interaction between users. One user did respond to the question regarding which principles should make up a code of ethics, mentioning confidentiality, impartiality, accuracy, and integrity. Another mentioned impartiality, confidentiality, and professionalism in a thread in which the question about the correct and incorrect behavior by public service interpreters was asked. Furthermore, one user stated that public service interpreters should always mention the code of ethics “to avoid confusion,” and shared a paper he had written on this subject, together with all of the Facebook users (<http://es.scribd.com/doc/101441857/Ethical-Issues-in-Public-Service-Interpreting>).

The following points should be highlighted regarding the aforementioned results:

1. Through various social media platforms, knowledge and awareness were spread on the issues related to the practice and the ethics surrounding PSIT professionals, and PSIT was consequently made more visible.
2. Ethics was a topic that was greatly followed by users.
3. In general, a lack of awareness regarding the codes of conduct of public service translators and interpreters and the basic principles they entail was evident.
4. Nonetheless, PSIT professionals are aware of the dilemmas caused by their jobs.
5. Moreover, four basic and common principles were identified by users, including confidentiality, impartiality, fidelity, and integrity.
6. All of the information provided during the three days of this event has been registered on the social media platforms used and can be referenced and outlined at any time.

2.3. Global E-Party en TISP, 3rd Edition

In November 2014, the third edition was organized. The motto was “Learn and Train” (in Spanish, “(In)formate”), and it was dedicated to promoting information and encouraging training regarding PSIT.

Figure 4. *Global E-Party en TISP* flyer 3rd edition. Issued in the University of Alcalá and through social media and by e-mail.

On this occasion, the length of the event was reduced and held over the course of two days via Twitter and Facebook, and the goal was to concentrate all efforts on these two social networking services.

- Facebook: There were 185 users in total sharing 24 posts, and the rise of participation in this medium during this period was not very significant.

Not only did different discussions arise from direct questions asked in these 20 posts, but also different resources were shared in order to promote more spontaneous discussions by allowing the participants to take initiative. To demonstrate this, some of the most relevant publications that encourage spontaneous Facebook participation should be outlined. The following are some of the most noted direct questions that were asked: 1) “Do you think there should be a certification system in Spain that would only allow professionals to practice in the PSIT sector?” 2) “Which criteria should be met in order to obtain this certification?” 3) “What are the most relevant differences between conference interpreter training and public service interpreter training?” 4) “Do you think continuous training is necessary for a public service translator/interpreter?” 5) “How can a professional continue to improve their skills in this field?” 6) “Should public service translators/interpreters specialize in one particular sector or is it really possible to practice in court, legal, education, healthcare, administrative, and social settings?” As can be observed, these questions were designed to encourage awareness and reflection on the importance of information in the practice of PSIT.

Among the resources shared, it is worth mentioning a three-part video titled *Medical Interpreter Training: A Clear Voice for Those in Need* (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hF2UiQREWD0>), a documentary titled *Qualified Interpreters for Quality Health Care* (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4VkJnyBqKeo>), a parody titled *Using a Medical Interpreter* (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D9s3sl5AoMg&feature=player_embedded), and a website called *SaludInmigrantes* (www.saludinmigrantes.es). These resources show the urgent need for qualified linguistic mediators within the public service field, especially in healthcare settings.

Despite the fact that there was not a lot of participation/interaction, the statistics show that the posts reached a significant number of people. For example, the second part of the video *Medical Interpreter Training: A Clear Voice for Those in Need* (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hAkwN3jOgdA>) was viewed by 422 people, making it the most successful post of the 3rd edition. The average following for the 24 posts was 101 people.

Although there were only a handful of posts, they demonstrated a consensus of opinion by participants who felt that there is a need for regulation in PSIT as a profession and that training is an essential part of professional development. The following are excerpts taken from some of the most significant posts regarding these opinions: “PS interpreters need specialized training in technical language (medical, legal) and should also take stress management courses”; “Yes, a certification system should be created for PSIT professionals”; “From among basic requirements, the following should be considered, at the very least: minimum age, 18, minimum education, baccalaureate ideal, MA, certified proficiency in at least two working languages, specialized course in PSIT with at least 60 in-person training hours completed, emotional intelligence such as self-knowledge, self-regulation, etc., and social skills such as empathy, compassion, cooperation, and an ability to work in stressful situations. Passing a comprehensive written and oral test which measures a wide range of skills and abilities would be ideal”; “Doctors are also responsible for bad practices.”

By June 8th, 2015, the number of Facebook likes had not stopped rising and is now at 190. This fact confirms that the open lines in this network are still in use and that there is some public interest even after the session has closed, despite the fact that active participation is low. All of this would lead to the conclusion that the role of Facebook is even bigger than what was initially intended (which was to spark extensive discussions among

unlimited numbers of participants). It appears that this social networking service now acts as a point of reflection that is still effective, even as time passes. All of these open posts are still viewed and taken on board by the followers of the Facebook profile.

- With regard to Twitter, it is worth mentioning that 229 followers were acquired, and 228 tweets were posted in total during this 3rd edition of the *Global E-Party en TISP*, ultimately giving the @GlobalPartyTISP account a total of 987 tweets. Once again, there was a significant rise in this social networking service.

Some of the key questions posted were “Which is more important for working in #TISP: training or experience?,” “How can we control quality in #TISP?,” and “Should translators/interpreters working in the PS sector receive specific training in this field?” (#TISPformación). From these first debates, and many other parallel debates stemming from them thereafter, the view among Twitter users on the importance of training in this field became evident. Some of the most notable responses supporting this view included the following: “They should train before they start and keep training while they work”; “Who is going to train the professionals? PSIT isn’t recognized”; “An interpreter in the USA got the wrong address and the patient died. The interpreter is in prison now”; “It wouldn’t be a bad idea to organize a meeting/get together with public service interpreters from all over the country”; “‘Thematic’ professional associations concentrate their efforts on one sector of the profession and fight to improve it”; “If conference interpreters make a mistake they might look bad, but if a PSIT makes a mistake, someone could die.”

Evidently, although there is no clear order of interaction or of the topics to which they are responding, these tweets show the demand among translators and interpreters for specific training in PSIT and for its development. As shown by different participants, a mistake in PSIT oftentimes has more serious consequences than in any other translation/interpreting specialty, for which reason it is even harder to understand why so little training exists in PSIT and why it is practiced by untrained and unqualified people. This collection of responses gives rise to some possible future research topics which would cover demands being made by professionals regarding the information and training surrounding PSIT.

The main conclusions drawn based on these results include the following:

1. Users demanded more information and training on PSIT.
2. They complained about the current training that is offered.
3. They wanted to learn more about PSIT, and they wanted it to be more visible and accessible to them.
4. They enjoyed following the posts/discussions through Facebook, even if they did not actively participate.
5. Twitter was, once again, the social networking service that was most used by participants.

2.4. Global E-Party en TISP, 4th Edition

A new edition was put together once again in November 2015, and the motto was “The Voice of the Two Parties” (“La voz de las dos partes”). This time, the *Global E-Party* was dedicated to facilitating communication between public service providers and public service translators/interpreters.

Figure 5. *Global E-Party en TISP* flyer 4th edition. Issued in the University of Alcalá and through social media and by e-mail.

This event lasted two days, and the objective was to once again foster active participation, as was done the previous year. Twitter and Facebook continued to be used during this edition, and YouTube was once again added in order to create audiovisual materials about PSIT and promote its visibility through a different channel. This year, YouTube’s role went beyond advertising, as was the case during the first year.

- YouTube: A specific channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCDi6O8AaiTpJeiVOQGZ2Gww>) was created and comprised 18 videos recorded in Spanish, Portuguese, Arabic, Mandarin, and Spanish Sign

Language. Through these videos, public service providers and public service translators and interpreters invited viewers to participate in the *Global E-Party en TISP*. This video, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-BiHv9XofeY>, was the most visited by users, with 213 visits.

- Facebook: During the days of the event, 21 posts were published and 110 new users joined, increasing the total number of likes to 295. This fourth edition had, consequently, a smaller number of posts but a greater number of followers. Coincidentally, the post that had the most followers, with a total of 910 visits, was the same video that was most visited on YouTube (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zl2i_pfvfBE). Discussions on this social networking service were not extensive during this edition, and they were created under the hashtags #TISPmed and #TISPsoc. Nonetheless, the number of materials shared was very relevant. An intriguing interview containing four direct questions was conducted with Nicoletta Spinolo regarding her experiences as they related to PSIT and the daily summaries about the most important published conclusions that were drawn from the event.

- Twitter: During the fourth edition of this event, the Twitter profile page gained 95 followers, obtaining a total of 324 followers. In addition, 584 tweets were posted on this account, bringing the total to 1,571 tweets—the highest number of tweets out of any of the four editions held up to this point in time. Only three hashtags were used to focus the participation on the main subjects chosen for this edition and for Facebook, including #TISP, #TISPmed, and #TISPsoc.

Under the hashtag #TISPmed, the participants discussed the status of PSIT as it pertains to healthcare settings, in addition to the insufficient training offers, the difficulties which characterize this setting, the opinions of the healthcare providers who work inadequately with translators and interpreters, the particular situations surrounding the lives of healthcare translators/interpreters, and codes of ethics.

With regard to the hashtag #TISPsoc, it is worth noting that it was a well-received topic, although not to the same extent as #TISPmed. Interestingly, participants associated this subject with migrants and refugees, demonstrating certain levels of difficulty when it came to defining social settings. They explained that these settings do not have a good status, and some confusion arose in some of the comments that were made due to all of the contexts that social settings entail. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that all of the participants discussed the erroneous and negative attitudes of the Spanish Government and the governments of other countries when it comes to managing the current massive migration.

The main conclusions drawn from these direct results include the following:

1. The *Global E-Party en TISP* is an event that continues to work even after four years, and its participants demand its continuation. Two days are enough to hold the event and promote active participation.
2. Social media platforms are used more frequently in the morning, and this is a fact that has been observed in all of the editions. Twitter continues to be the most used social networking service utilized in this event. The addition of YouTube was a good idea.
3. The fourth edition has been the edition that was best received by participants, possibly due to its level of technicality (healthcare and social settings) and the originality of the topics that were presented, as noted by some of the participants. They continued complaining about the current training offers and status of PSIT, as was the case in previous editions.
4. Overall, the participants are hopeful that the current situation surrounding PSIT will improve.
5. Healthcare settings are seen as more appealing to participants than social settings. They also feel as if healthcare settings have a more positive status.
6. Due to the participants' appreciation toward the level of technicality of this edition, the possibility of dedicating the fifth edition to other types of PSIT settings is being greatly considered.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Results obtained from the analysis of the four editions thus far show that the *Global E-Party en TISP* is well received and not only allows knowledge to be shared regarding PSIT, but also gives rise to different research perspectives and topics that arise from the debates themselves.

Moreover, some common conclusions pertaining to all four editions held until now can be drawn:

1. Twitter is the social networking service that is most favored and used by participants due to its “quick feedback” nature.
2. An average of almost 100 users (to be precise, 96) read the posts shared on Facebook even if they do not actively participate by discussing the topics.
3. People like this kind of event because over the 60 % of the participants of the first edition continued to participate in the other three editions. This has allowed different topics regarding PSIT to be dealt with by students, professionals, researchers, and even inexperienced individuals.

4. A rise in the number of followers across all used social media platforms has been observed every year not only during the days of the event, but also throughout the year (at least 10 users/year, depending on the specific edition).
5. Although there is still a weak presence of PSIT in social media, there is increasing interest from various groups.
6. Consequently, this type of event favors PSIT media visibility, and this increased awareness could contribute to its professionalization. Nonetheless, further research is required in order to prove this hypothesis.
7. Attempts will be made in the next few years to repeat this experience and organize more editions of the *Global E-Party en TISP*. All readers are invited to be active participants from this point forward.

IV. PROPOSALS FOR THE NEXT EDITIONS OF THE *GLOBAL E-PARTY EN TISP*

In order to raise the visibility of PSIT on social media, it is proposed for the next editions of the *Global E-Party en TISP*:

- Use Twitter as the main platform to divulge contents regarding PSIT due to its popularity and success in this kind of event;
- keep Facebook as an informative platform;
- choose polemic and different mottos in order to promote the discussion in a comfortable way;
- ask for the participants' opinion about the proposal of specific subjects about PSIT and take into count them;
- add different language combinations to interact in this event and to make in more international.

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